

SHORE

Empower students as the agents of change

D6.1 Submission and Management Platform

6/12/2023

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F6S

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Executive summary

This document is a deliverable of the SHORE Project, funded under the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101112815 and it describes in detail navigation in F6S submission system used in SHORE Open Calls.

Deliverable “Submission and Management Platform” (D6.1) reports in detail navigation in submission & management platform and guides through all sections of proposal and system for SHORE Open Calls.

1. Navigating F6S platform

To facilitate the proposal submissions, SHORE project has opted for the F6S platform, a widely recognized tool in the realm of project funding, favored by both Investors and Accelerators for supporting inventive ventures. Accounts established on F6S submission platform dedicated to SHORE are as follows:

- SHORE Project - basic F6S info page

<https://www.f6s.com/shore-project>

- SHORE Open Call 1 Page (hosting Application Form button):

<https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1>

To initiate the submission process, applicants simply follow the link: <https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1/apply>. This will lead applicants to the dedicated F6S submission page, where a welcoming screen will be displayed.

Figure 1 F6S Welcoming screen (registration invitation)

Applicants will have to create an account and sign up, by using one out of three options available: Facebook, LinkedIn, or email. If the applicant will choose Facebook or LinkedIn, a pop-up will request permission for F6S to authenticate you through the selected platform. Opting for email requires creating a password and providing your first and last name.

Auto-Save Feature

The application form incorporates an "auto-save" function that operates as follows: any changes made to the form are automatically saved as edited. The form can be closed and returned to at any time, using the same F6S credentials. Unlimited changes can be made until application is submitted. No modifications are possible after submission.

Upon connecting to F6S, the application form will become accessible. Please note that our open call only allows for single applicants, such as individual representatives of the school applying for the SHORE programme, who can provide additional information about their background via their F6S profile.

Figure 2 "Update your profile" option on the F6S platform

Figure 3 Overview of the F6S individual profile

2. Application form

Disclaimer: The images of the online application form provided here are intended for reference purposes only! Questions listed in this document are only indicative.

After creating a profile, the application form will be accessible. The SHORE online application form is divided into several sections, both with optional and mandatory fields (marked with *), and different technical modules for answering, depending on each individual question (short/long answers; checkboxes and drop-down lists, upload (“Choose a File”) buttons).

2.1. Sections Individual Info and School Info

In this section, the school applying for the programme is able to provide more administrative information about its establishment and the individual submitting the application.

INDIVIDUAL INFO

1 Full Name *

2 Email Address *

3 Your role/position in the school

SCHOOL INFO

4 Full Name

5 Street Address *

6 School website

7 School info email *

8 VAT number *

9 Registration number
Please provide the school's registration number or any official identification that proves its legal status as an educational institution.

Figure 4 Sections Individual and School Info

2.2. Section Eligibility

In this section, the school applying for the programme is able to provide more information about its eligibility for the SHORE programme, as requested.

ELIGIBILITY

- 10 **Type of school ***
- Elementary School Secondary School
- 11 **Please specify the age range of students involved in the school's curriculum**
-
- 12 **Geographical area of the school ***
- Please state if the school is legally established in one of SHORE Target Areas, according to Open Call Guide for Applicants
- Baltic Sea Area Black Sea Area Mediterranean Sea Area
- Danube River Area Rhine River Area
- 13 **If selected Baltic Sea Area, please state the country in which the school is legally established. ***
- NOTE: Eligible Countries from Baltic Sea Area Involve Contracting Parties according to the 1992 Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area (Helsinki Convention): helcom.fi/wpcontent/uploads/2019/06/HelsinkiConvention_July-2014.pdf
-
- 14 **If selected Black Sea Area, please state the country in which the school is legally established. ***
- NOTE: Eligible Countries from Black Sea Area Involve Contracting Parties according to Summit Declaration on Black Sea Economic Cooperation: www.bsecorganization.org/UploadedDocuments/BsecAtAGlance/Istanbul1992New.pdf
-
- 15 **If selected Mediterranean Sea Area, please state the country in which the school is legally established. ***
- NOTE: Eligible Countries from Mediterranean Sea Area Involve Contracting Parties according to UNEP-MAP (Barcelona Convention): wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/70996/StatusOfSignaturesAndRatifications_20201029.pdf
-
- 16 **If selected Danube River Area, please state the country in which the school is legally established. ***
- NOTE: Eligible Countries from Danube River Area Involve Contracting Parties according to the Danube River Protection Convention (DRPC): www.icpdr.org/sites/default/files/DRPC%20English%20over.pdf
-
- 17 **If selected Rhine River Area, please state the country in which the school is legally established. ***
- NOTE: Eligible Countries from Rhine River Area Involve Contracting Parties according to the 1999 Convention on the Protection of the Rhine: www.ksr.org/fileadmin/user_upload/DKDM/Dokumente/Rechtliche_Basis/EN/legal_En_1999.pdf
-
- 18 **Accreditation in the European Network of Blue Schools ***
- Please state the school's accreditation status in the European Network of Blue Schools, according to Open Call Guide for Applicants.
- If a second option was selected, then proceed to demonstrate how the school intends to meet the prerequisites to become accredited member by the time of completion of the project, as part of their Technical Proposal.
- NOTE: The Network of European Blue Schools is established under EU4Ocean coalition: maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/ocean-literacy-and-blue-skills/ocean-literacy/network-blue-schools/become-european-blue-school_en
- The applicant is an accredited member of the European Network of Blue Schools The applicant aspires to be a member of the European Network of Blue Schools

Figure 5 Section Eligibility

2.3. Section Proposal Info

In this section, the school applying for the programme is able to provide more information about the proposal that the applicant is submitting to SHORE Open Call, as requested, as well as upload the requested SHORE Proposal Template.

PROPOSAL INFO

19 **Proposal Acronym ***

Please provide your proposal acronym

20 **Please select the topic of your project ***

The SHORE – Open Call #1 is open to proposals that address at least one topic and subtopic of the open call, according to Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants.

- Topic # 1 Sea-based activities
- Topic # 2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter
- Topic # 3 Biodiversity
- Topic # 4 Climate Change
- Topic #5 Sustainable use of water resources

21 **If selected Topic # 1, please select related sub-topic of your project ***

- Fisheries and Aquaculture
- Coastal Tourism
- Marine and River Transport and Shipping
- Biotechnology

22 **If selected Topic # 2, please select related sub-topic of your project ***

- Oil rigs
- Heavy Metals
- Plastics & Microplastics
- Various Wastes from Cruise Ships
- Various Wastes from Cities

23 **If selected Topic # 3, please select related sub-topic of your project ***

- Migration of the Species
- Damage to Coral Reefs and Riverbeds
- Microplastics Uptake by Aquatic Animals
- Erosion and Flooding
- Preserve biodiversity in waters

24 **If selected Topic # 4, please select related sub-topic of your project ***

- Water-body acidification
- Eutrophication
- Rising Temperature
- Droughts
- Rise in Sea Levels

25 **If selected Topic # 5, please select related sub-topic of your project ***

- Renewable Marine and Water Energy
- Nuclear power plants on shores
- Drinking water
- Food from sea and water

26 **Proposal Template (Max file size 30MB.) ***

Please upload a pdf of Proposal Template with all sections filled out, according to Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants. Please use Annex 2.1 - SHORE Proposal Template available here: INSERT website link.

Figure 6 Section Proposal Info

2.4. Section Requirements to join SHORE Programme and Other

In this section, the school applying for the programme is able to provide more information about its fulfilments of requirements, to join the SHORE programme, as requested. In addition, the applicant is welcomed to provide other information for reference purpose and open call statistics only.

REQUIREMENTS TO JOIN SHORE PROGRAMME

- 27 **If selected, do you agree to sign the "Annex 4 - SHORE Declaration of Honour" ***
 I CONFIRM that I accept all conditions in ANNEX 4 - SHORE Declaration of Honour and information contained therein and that it will be provided signed and stamped if this proposal will be accepted for funding. Click here to visualise this document: [Insert PDF link](#)
- Yes
 No
- 28 **Acceptance of the SHORE Open Call rules ***
 Click here to visualise the Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants available at: [INSERT PDF link](#)
- Yes, I have reviewed and accepted all the conditions of Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants
- 29 **Agree on GDPR ***
 Available at eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/
- Yes, I accept
- 30 **Double Funding ***
 Proposals from applicants and linked schools (see table of Terms and Definitions) must demonstrate that there is no risk of double funding. The fundamental principle underpinning the rules for public expenditure in the EU states that no costs for the same activity can be funded twice from the EU budget, as defined in the Article 111 of Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1605/2002 of 25 June 2002 on the Financial Regulation.
- No risk of double funding
- 31 **Conflict of Interest ***
 Beneficiaries must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the sub-project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest.
- To the best of our knowledge, there is no conflict of interest

OTHER

- 32 **How did you find out about this call?**
- Social Media Referrals from other EU projects European Commission Communications
- F6S website SHORE Consortium Search Engine
- Event Other

Figure 7 Section Requirements to join SHORE Programme and Other

3. Submitting the application form

Once the application form is finished, applicants are allowed to submit it by clicking on the blue button below the page, as shown on Figure 8.

It is recommended to be on time and submit proposal through the F6S platform before the deadline of the respective open call. If the proposal is submitted correctly, the system will send a confirmation (SPAM folder should be checked additionally). Proposals submitted by any other means are ineligible, hence will not be evaluated.

OTHER

32 How did you find out about this call?

<input type="checkbox"/> Socia Media	<input type="checkbox"/> Referrals from other EU projects	<input type="checkbox"/> European Commission Communications
<input type="checkbox"/> F6S website	<input type="checkbox"/> SHORE Consortium	<input type="checkbox"/> Search Engine
<input type="checkbox"/> Event	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	

Recommendations ⓘ

Ask for new Recommendations ⓘ

Type name or email

[Request](#)

Are you done? Click below to finalize

[Connect with Milana & Joanna](#)

Figure 8 F6S Application submission button

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